

LEPIDOPTERA FAUNA OF NAMIBIA III: KATIMA MULILO, ZAMBEZI REGION

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Abstract

In total, 76 moth and 12 butterfly species from 14 superfamilies and three families, respectively, have been identified in and around Katima Mulilo, a town in northeastern Namibia. The most speciose families were Noctuidae (22 spp.) and Geometridae (9 spp.). Forty-three species were recorded for the first time in Namibia, including 19 from the family Noctuidae and 7 from the family Geometridae. The present study suggests that the moth fauna of Namibia, especially of the families Noctuidae and Geometridae, is largely unrecorded in the Zambezi Region, and perhaps elsewhere in Namibia.

KEYWORDS: Lepidoptera, biodiversity, distribution, moths, Katima Mulilo, Caprivi Strip

Introduction

This paper presents findings from studies that are part of an ongoing project on Namibian moths and butterflies (Kopij, 2014, Kopij & Paxton, 2019). It deals with Lepidoptera fauna in northeastern Namibia. To date, regular lepidopterological studies have not been conducted in this region (Kopij, 2017).

The only thorough lepidopterological inventory in Namibia was conducted in Brandberg (Mey, 2004, 2007), a massif in the Namib Desert of around 650 km², with its highest point at 2,573 m a. s. l. It lies within the Karoo-Namib floristic region. The inventory lists 683 species from 58 families (including 124 new species and 9 new genera).

Preliminary lepidopterological inventories have also been conducted in the Okavango River Valley in the Kavango Region (Kopij & Paxton, 2019) and the Cuvelai Drainage System in north-central Namibia (Kopij, 2014). Mey (2011) collected butterflies and moths from 80 sites distributed all over Namibia. However, only the more common species, a dozen or so at each site (about 100 species from 30 families, in total), were identified in these collections.

A few other inventories were limited to butterflies or the Saturniidae family. In 1991-2002, Braine (2002) recorded 76 butterfly species from 10 subfamilies in the Hobatere (320 km², mainly mopane savanna), on the western border of Etosha National Park. Oberprierer (1992 a,b) conducted a thorough inventory of moths from the family Saturniidae in the Kavango and Zambezi regions in NE Namibia.

Materials and Methods

Studies were conducted in the town of Katima Mulilo within its administrative boundaries. It is located in the far northeastern part of Namibia, in the Zambezi River Valley (17°30'S 24°16'E) at an altitude of 950 m a.s.l. The town was founded in 1935. It had 5,000 inhabitants in 1975, with the number growing to 46,406 in 2024.

The natural vegetation in the town comprises Kalahari woodland, Mopane savanna, and Zambezi riparian forest, but only small remnants persist, mainly along the banks of the Zambezi River. The town, however, is richly planted with a mix of indigenous and exotic trees and shrubs. The most common are fruit trees, such as mango, papaya, cassava, lemon, and bananas. Indigenous wild trees include, among many others: African teak (*Pterocarpus angolensis*), albizia (*Albizia* spp.), Kalahari apple leaf (*Lonchocarpus nelsii*), baobab (*Adansonia digitata*), wild syringa (*Burkea africana*), combretum (*Combretum* spp.), camelthorn (*Acacia erioloba*), corkwoods (*Commiphora* spp.), false mopane (*Guibourtia coleosperma*), jackal berry (*Diospyros mespiliformis*), knob-thorn (*Accacia nigrescens*), makalani palm (*Hyphaene petersiana*), manketti (*Schinziophyton rautanenii*), marula (*Sclerocarya birrea*), mopane (*Colophospermum mopane*), pod mahogany (*Azelia quanzensis*), silver cluster-leaf (*Terminalia sericea*), sausage tree (*Kigelia africana*), sycamore fig (*Ficus sycomorus*), white bauhinia (*Bauhinia petersiana*), Zambezi teak (*Baikiaea plurijuga*). The most common exotic trees are gums (*Eucalyptus* spp.), jacarandas (*Jacaranda* sp.), and she-oaks (*Casuarina* sp.) (Kopij, 2016).

The climate in Katima Mulilo can be classified as humid subtropical. The annual temperature for Katima Mulilo is 21°C. Average maximum temperature during the hottest month (September) is 35°C. The average annual rainfall is c. 700 mm, the highest in Namibia. Most of the rains fall between November and March (Mendelsohn & Roberts, 1997; Mendelsohn *et al.*, 2009).

Moths and butterflies were trapped by sweeping net and light 60W (cf. Kopij, 2005, 2014, Kopij & Paxton, 2019). The sampling was made throughout the year. The sex of the collected butterflies and moths has been determined whenever possible. The specimens have been deposited in the author's private collection.

As in Kopij (2005, 2014), the identification of moth species followed Pinhey (1979), Oberprierer (1995), and Picker *et al.* (2002); Pringle *et al.* (1994) and Woodhall (2005) were followed for butterflies.

Figure 1. Habitats in Katima Mulilo.

Results

Systematic review of species:

The systematics and nomenclature of all taxa follow Vari *et al.* (2002). For each species listed (identified), date of collection and a short note about its global distribution are given. Species indicated with an asterisk (*) are not included in the De Prins & De Prins (2024) database of African moths, while species indicated with a plus sign (+) are not included in the Irish (2024) database of Namibian moths and butterflies, which is more complete than that of De Prins & De Prins (2024). The following abbreviations are used in the 'Distribution' section: CP – Cape Province, EC – Eastern Cape, FS – Free State, KZN – KwaZulu Natal, L – Limpopo, M – Mpumalanga, NW – North-West Province, T – Transvaal.

Cossoidea

Family Cossidae

Zeuzerinae

***Azygophleps leopardina* Distant 1902**

Records: March 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Namibia, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Kenya.

Zygaenoidea

Family Limacodidae

Limacodinae

***+*Coenobasis amoena* Felder 1874**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: southern and eastern Africa.

***+*Latoia johannes* (Distant 1898)**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (CP, KZN, T), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Tanzania.

****Latoia vivida* (Walker 1865)**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN), Namibia, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Mozambique, Malawi.

Pyraloidea

Family Pyralidae

Pyralinae

+*Mittonia hampsoni* (Distant 1897)

Records: December 2014, 1 ex.; January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia.

Family Crambidae

Pyraustinae

***+*Pyrausta incoloralis* Guenee 1854**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Asia, Australia.

Spilomelinae

****Bocchoris inspersalis* (Zeller 1852)**

Records: December 2014, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa and southern Eurasia.

****Diaphania indica* (Saunders 1851) = *Glyphodes indica***

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, south-eastern Asia, Australia.

***+*Syllepte ovalis* (Walker 1859)**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.; March 2016, 1 ♀.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Asia.

****Terastia margaritis* Felder et Rogenhofer 1875**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique.

Geometroidea

Family Geometridae

Ennominae

***+*Epigynopteryx maeviaria maeviaria* (Guenee 1858)**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi.

***+*Menophra caeca* Prout 1913 = *Aphilopota mailaria* (Swinhoe 1904)**

Records: May 2016, 1 ♀ (much darker than 321 on plate 21 in Pinhey 1979).

Distribution: subsp.: South Africa (T), Mozambique, Zimbabwe.

***+*Xylopteryx oneili* Prout 1922**

Records: March 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia.

Family Sterrhinae

****Rhodometra sacraria* (Linnaeus 1767)**

Records: May 2015, 1 ex.; June 2015, 2 ex. January 2016, 1 ex.; May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Europe.

Family Larentiinae

***+*Eupithecia rediviva* Prout 1917**

Records: May 2015, 1 ex.; June 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Zimbabwe.

***+*Scopula curvimargo* (Warren 1900)**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Angola, Zimbabwe, Zambia.

Family Geometrinae

***+*Centrochia deprensa* (Prout 1913)**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (T), Zimbabwe.

***+*Mixocera viridans* Prout 1912**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.; March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Botswana, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Mozambique, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC).

****Neromia strigulosa* Prout 1925**

Records: January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (FS), Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe.

Drepanoidea

Family Drepanidae

Drepaninae

***+*Negera n. natalensis* (Felder 1874)**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

Hesperioidea

Family Hesperidae

Pyrginae

+*Netrobalane canopus* (Trimen 1864)

Records: April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Eswatini, Mozambique, Zimbabwe.

***Spialia secessus* (Trimen 1891)**

Records: October/November 2014, 1ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Zimbabwe.

Family Hesperiiinae

***Gegenes niso* (Linnaeus 1764)**

Records: April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over South Africa.

Papilionoidea

Family Pieridae

Pierinae

***Colotis amata calais* (Cramer 1775)**

Records: 05.06.2015, 1 ex., 1♂.

Distribution: sp.: all over Africa, southern Asia; subsp.: South Africa (KZN, M, L).

***Colotis antevippe gavis* (Wallengren 1857)**

Records: 05.06.2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: sp.: all over Africa; subsp.: South Africa (WC, EC, KZN, T).

***Colotis danae annae* (Wallengren 1857)**

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: sp.: all over Africa; subsp.: South Africa (T, EC, KZN), Eswatini, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique.

***Colotis regina* (Trimen 1863)**

Records: December 2014, 1 ex.

Distribution: widespread, but rare. South Africa (KZN, T, NW), Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique.

***Belenois aurota* (Fabricius 1793)**

Records: 05.06.2015, 1 ex.; April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over southern Africa.

***Belenois gidica* (Godart 1819)**

Records: Jan. 2016, 1 ex. (forma *abyssinica*)

Distribution: South Africa (KZN), Eswatini, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Namibia.

***Eurema brigitta* (Stoll 1870)**

Records: March 2016, 1♂.

Distribution: sp.: all over Africa; subsp.: all over southern Africa.

+*Mylothris agathina* (Cramer 1779)

Records: June 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (EC, KZN, T), Eswatini, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique.

Family Nymphalidae

Biblidinae

***Byblia anvatara acheloia* (Wallengren 1857)**

Records: April 2016, 1♂.

Distribution: South Africa (EC, KZN, T), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Namibia.

***Byblia ilythya* (Drury 1773)**

Records: April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over South Africa.

Limenitidinae

+*Hamanumida daedalus* (Fabricius 1775)

Records: April 2016, 1♀.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Eswatini, Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia.

***Neptis jordani* Neave 1910**

Records: December 2014, 1ex.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN only; rare.

Nymphalinae

***Junonia oenona oenona* (Linnaeus 1758)**

Records: December 2014, 1♀.

Distribution: common in southern Africa.

Figure 2. A – *Junonia o. oenona*, B – *Neptis jordani*

Bombycoidea

Family Lasiocampidae

Lasiocampinae

***+*Bombycopsis indecora indecora* (Walker 1865)**

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa; common.

Sena parva* (Aurivillius 1921) = *Chilena parva

Records: January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (NC), Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe.

Sena p. prompta* (Walker 1855) = *Chilena prompta

Records: December 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Botswana, Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Kenya.

***+*Streblote cristata* (Stoll 1782) = *Nadiasa carinata* (Wallengren 1860)**

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (Cape, KZN, T), Botswana, Zimbabwe, eastern Africa.

+*Streblote polydora* (Druce 1888) = *Nadiasa polydora

Records: May 2016, 1♀.

Distribution: South Africa, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Tanzania.

****Trichopisthia igneotincta* (Aurivillius 1909) = *Craspia igneotincta***

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Malawi, Angola.

Gastropachinae

***Epitrabala n. nyassana* (Aurivillius 1909)**

Records: March 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi, Democratic Republic of Congo.

***Gastroplakaeis meridionalis* Aurivillius 1901**

Records: March 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: Namibia, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia.

Eupterotidae

Striphnopteryginae

***+*Phiala marshalli* Aurivillius 1904**

Records: December 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi, eastern Africa.

***+*Phiala pretoriana* Wichgraf 1908**

Records: October/November 2014, 2 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (T), Zimbabwe, Botswana.

Family Bombycidae

Bombycinae

***+*Ocinara ficicola* (Westwood et Ormerod 1889)**

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: eastern and northern South Africa.

Family Saturniidae

Saturniinae

***+*Athletes semialba* (Sonthonnax1904)**

Records: December 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Zambia, Mal, Tanzania.

***+*Goodia kuntzei* (Dewitz 1881)**

Records: March 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (T), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Angola, Zambia, Malawi, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Tanzania, Kenya.

***Heniocha dyops* (Maassen 1872)**

Records: December 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, eastern Africa

****Imbrasia belina* (Westwood 1849) = *Gonimbrasia belina***

Records: March 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

Figure 3. A – *Imbrasia belina*; B – *Heniocha dyops*; C – *Goodia kuntzei*; D – *Agrius convolvuli*.

Family Sphingidae

Sphinginae

Agrius convolvuli* (Linnaeus 1758) = *Herse convolvuli

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, Eurasia, Australia.

Polyptychoides g. grayi* (Walker 1856) = *Polyptychus grayi

Records: October/November 2014, 2 ex.

Distribution: southern and eastern Africa.

***+*Pseudandriasa mutata* (Walker 1855)**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN).

Macroglossinae

****Daphnis nerii* (Linnaeus 1758) = *Deilephila nerii* Linnaeus 1758**

Records: April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Eurasia.

****Nephele comma* Hopffer 1857**

Records: December 2015, 2 ex.; January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***+*Nephele funebris* (Fabricius 1793)**

Records: December 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

****Rhodafra opheltes* (Cramer 1780)**

Records: March 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over South Africa.

+*Temnora namaqua* Rothschild et Jordan 1903

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over South Africa.

Noctuoidea

Family Notodontidae

Notodontinae

***+*Antheua ornata* (Walker 1865)**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi, eastern Africa.

Family Arctiidae

Arctiinae

***+*Cretonotos punctivitta* (Walker 1855)**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.; April/May 2016, 2 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi, Angola.

***+*Ilmodes astriga* Hampson 1916**

Records: March 2016, 2 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Zimbabwe, Zambia, Mozambique.

Paralacydes arborifera* (Butler 1875) = *Maenas arborifera

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.; March 2015, 1 ex.; March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: southern and eastern Africa.

Saenura flava* (Wallengren 1858) = *Diacrisia flava

Records: January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (CP, T), Namibia, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi.

+*Spilosoma lineatum* (Walker 1855) = *Diacrisia lineatum*

Records: January 2016, 1 ex.; March 2016, 2 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (CP, KZN, T), Botswana, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Mozambique, Malawi, Tanzania, Kenya.

***Utethesia pulchella* (Linnaeus 1758)**

Records: February 2015, 6 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Eurasia, Australia.

Family Noctuidae

Catocalinae

***+*Acantholipes trimeni* Felder et Rogenhofer 1874**

Records: May 2015, 1 ex.; May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Botswana, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi.

***+*Achaea catella* Guenee 1852**

Records: April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***+*Achaea echo* (Walker 1858)**

Records: January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***+*Anticarsia irrorata* (Fabricius 1781)**

Records: November 2014, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Asia, Australia.

***+*Calliodes pretiosissima* Holland 1892**

Records: February 2015, 1♂.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Namibia, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Mozambique, Malawi, Uganda.

***+*Cerocala vermiculosa* Herrich-Schaeffer 1854**

Records: December 2014, 1 ex.; March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (CP, FS, T), Botswana, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Zambia.

***+*Cortyta canescens* Walker 1858**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.; March 2016, 1♀.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Zimbabwe, eastern Africa.

+*Dysgonia angularis* (Buisduval 1833) = *Caranilla angularis

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

+*Dysgonia algira* (Linnaeus 1767) = *Parallelia algira

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Eurasia.

***+*Entomogramma pardus* Guenee 1852**

Records: May 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

+*Eudocima materna* (Linnaeus 1767) = *Othreis materna

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Eurasia, Australia; common.

Grammodes stolidia* (Fabricius 1775) = *Prodotis stolidia

Records: March 2016, 2 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Eurasia.

***+*Mocis mayeri* (Boisduval 1833)**

Records: April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

+*Ophiusa dianiris* (Guenee 1852) = *Anua dinarius

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: southern and eastern Africa.

+*Ophiusa mejanesi* (Guenee 1852) = *Trichanua mejanesi

Records: March 2015, 3 ex.; April 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Sphingomorpha chlorea* (Cramer 1777)**

Records: February 2015, 2 ex.; January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: common all over Africa and southern Asia.

Hadeninae

***Diaphone eumela* (Stoll 1781)**

Records: January 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (CP, KZN), Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Malawi.

+*Leucania polyrabda* (Hampson 1905) = *Mythimna polyrabda

Records: May 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: South Africa (KZN, T), Zimbabwe, Zambia.

Chloephorinae

***+*Xanthodes graellsii* Feisthamel 1837**

Records: February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Eurasia.

Acontiinae

***+*Eublemma anachoresis* (Wallengren 1863)**

Records: May 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa, southern Asia, Australia.

Acronictinae

***+*Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval 1833)**

Records: March 2016, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

Family Agaristidae

+*Aegoceropsis fervida* (Walker 1854) = *Aegocera fervida

Records: KM, February 2015, 1 ex.

Distribution: all over Africa.

Discussion

In total, 88 lepidopteran species were identified in the Kavango region, 76 moth and 12 butterfly species. The list is far from complete. The most speciose families were Noctuidae (22 spp.), and Geometridae (9 spp.), which are also the most abundant in Namibia (Irish, 2024).

Table I. Number of Lepidoptera species recorded in Katima Mulilo (KM, this study) compared with that recorded in Namibia (Irish 2024) and southern Africa (SA; Vari *et al.* 2002).

Family	KM	Namibia	SA
Arctiidae	6	56	227
Bombycidae	1	1	5
Cossidae	1	38	56
Crambidae	5	90	455
Drepanidae	1	1	7
Eupterotidae	2	5	62
Geometridae	9	114	1105
Hesperiidae	3	43	130
Lasiocampidae	8	37	127
Limacodidae	3	23	119
Noctuidae	22	218	1608
Notodontidae	1	26	199
Nymphalidae	5	69	268
Pieridae	8	33	60
Pyrilidae	1	108	562
Saturniidae	4	29	75
Sphingidae	8	28	105
Total	88	919	5170

Forty-three species were recorded for the first time in Namibia (i.e. no records in the databases of Irish (2024) or De Prins & De Prins (2024)). This includes 19 species from the family Noctuidae and seven from the family Geometridae. An additional 12 species were recorded that are not listed by De Prins & De Prins (2024) but are included in Irish (2024), while 6 species listed by De Prins & De Prins (2024) were not found in Irish's database. It is important to point out that Irish (2024) lists 1869 species (including 493 endemic Lepidoptera species and 224 butterfly species) for Namibia, while De Prins & De Prins (2024) lists 510 moth species for Namibia in contrast to 29972 moth species across 9155 genera and 137 families recorded in the entire African continent. Kopij (2017) records 890 Lepidoptera species for Namibia. The discrepancy in recorded species numbers is largely due to the De Prins & De Prins (2024) database being less comprehensive than the Irish (2024) database, although both are continuously updated.

The present study (Table I) suggests that the moth fauna of Namibia is largely under-recorded. In contrast, the butterfly fauna is well documented, but even in this group, a dozen or more additional species may still remain to be discovered.

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ФАУНА ЛЕПТИРА НАМИБИЈЕ III: КАТИМА МУЛИЛО, РЕГИЈА ЗАМБЕЗИ

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Извод

Идентификовано је укупно 76 врста ноћних лептира и 12 врста дневних лептира из 14 надпородица и три породице, у области града Катима Мулило, на североистоку Намибије. Најбројније породице биле су Noctuidae (22 врсте) и Geometridae (9 врста). Четрдесет три врсте су први пут забележене у Намибији, укључујући 19 из породице Noctuidae и 7 из породице Geometridae. Ова студија указује да је фауна ноћних лептира Намибије, посебно из породица Noctuidae и Geometridae, углавном слабо истражена у региону Замбези, а вероватно и у другим регионима Намибије.

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